

FINANCIAL ADMINISTRATION RULES AND TRANSPARENCY IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The public sector has been plagued with accusations of misappropriation of cash and this has continued to weaken the transparency role of the government. Governments, in a bid to restore their image, have continued to put in place policies to curb financial leakages and improve transparency in the management of public funds. Hence, this study examined the effect of financial administration rules on transparency in federal Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs) in Ekiti State; specifically, the rules such as the treasury single account system, government integrated financial management information system, and integrated personnel payroll information system policies. The study adopted the primary data method by administering the questionnaire. The study used a survey research design to gather information. The population for the study is 253 heads and directors of federal ministries, departments, and agencies in Ekiti State, while the sample size is one hundred and fifty (150) heads and directors of MDAs chosen through purposive sampling technique because study data were gathered directly from targeted respondents. The data were analyzed using descriptive and ordinary least square regression. The findings of the study revealed that a treasury single account with a p-value of $0.05 < p < 0.05$ had a positive significant effect on transparency. Government integrated financial information system with a p-value of $0.000 < p < 0.05$ had a significant effect on transparency and an integrated personnel payroll information system with a p-value of $0.000 < p < 0.05$ had a positive significant effect on transparency. The study established that treasury single account, government integrated financial information system, and integrated personnel payroll information system which are the variables used to measure financial administration rules do influence transparency. The study recommended that the government ensure that they maintain these financial administration rules and that they have proved to have an impact on the government's cash-controlling potential and enhanced transparency and credibility of the government.

Keywords:

Financial administration rules, treasury single account, government integrated financial management information system, integrated personnel payroll system and transparency

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In a society rife with diversions and evolving obligations, the notion of openness appears to be a diminished virtue universally. Effective financial administration regulations are essential for ensuring accountability, preventing financial mismanagement, and maximising the utilisation of public funds for national development (Ibitoye et al., 2025). A strong framework for financial oversight is not merely a necessity but a fundamental element of sustainable governance (Abubakar et al., 2025). To accomplish these objectives, a government must establish a systematic mechanism to validate its financial administration process. Public transparency is a fundamental principle in public sector governance, as government operations revolve around revenue collection and the allocation of monies for the social and economic requirements of residents (Chizoba & Onuora, 2025). Ensuring effective management of government-held money and the provision of accurate stewardship reports has been a challenge in many developing

nations, including Nigeria. Ibekaku-Nwagwu (2025) claimed that substantial financial losses had occurred owing to mismanagement and embezzlement in Nigeria. Simon et al. (2025) asserted that financial administration rules minimising idle cash balances, strategically investing surplus cash, and optimising arrangements to fulfill financial commitments promptly. Financial administration rules as articulated by Akpanowo and Mbobo (2025) described as the formulation of administrative strategies to optimising the number of liquid assets held by government entities to avert disruptions in the economic cycle. The Nigerian government has been acting against this threat by keeping its finances in check through measures like the Treasury Single Account (TSA) and the Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (Titus et al., 2025; Amahalu et al., 2022).

The Nigerian government implemented the Treasury Single Account system to enhance financial administration as a scheme that all government revenues should be collected from a singular account held by the Central Bank of Nigeria. This policy has been documented in the dispersion of accounts throughout many ministries, departments, and agencies, rendering it unfeasible for the government to ascertain the total number of accounts and their respective balances (Ibitoye et al., 2025; Kure & Salisu, 2024). This approach enables the government to comprehensively understand its entire cash, facilitating effective planning and expenditure and focused anti-corruption efforts via the Government-Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS) enhance the procurement, distribution, utilisation, and conversion of public financial resources through automated, effective, efficient, and economical information systems, while modernising fiscal processes with superior methods, techniques, and information technology (Adeniji et al., 2025; Okolie & Egbon, 2025). The Government-Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS) is a cohesive digital platform intended to optimise and automate the financial management procedures of governmental entities (Amahalu et al., 2022). The GIFMIS methodology consolidates essential operations, including budgeting, accounting, procurement, and auditing, into a unified system, facilitating real-time monitoring and administration of public finances. The method improves openness and effectiveness in the administration of government resources, ensuring that money is allocated according to authorised budgets and under financial standards (Ibekaku-Nwagwu, 2025).

The difficulty challenge confronting financial administration and transparency in the MDAs in Nigeria is the absence of effective fiscal management. Inadequate cash flow management leads to resource misallocations, resulting in postponed project execution and the failure to deliver timely financial reporting. Insufficient monitoring and inadequate internal controls adversely affect transparency and increase the likelihood of corruption. The majority of MDAs encounter challenges in adhering to financial laws due to uneven policy enforcement and inadequate monitoring capability (Huang et al., 2025). The absence of transparency, openness, and coordination in financial administration undermines public trust and adversely affects governmental functioning owing to the ineffective allocation of resources. The misuse of information results in diminished public resources and an inequitable distribution of wealth. Therefore, it is essential to examine if this governmental expectation has been fulfilled, as this is the sole means to validate governmental efforts. This study seeks to investigate the subsequent research questions: What impact does the Treasury Single Account (TSA) have on transparency inside the federal Ministries, Departments, and Agencies in Ekiti State, Nigeria? To what degree does the Government Integrated Financial Information System (GIFMIS) influence transparency among the federal ministries, departments, and agencies in Ekiti State, Nigeria? What is the impact of the Integrated Personnel Payroll System (IPPIS)? The primary aim of this study was to examine the correlation between financial administration regulations and transparency inside federal ministries, departments, and agencies in Nigeria. The study investigated the impact of the treasury single account on transparency in federal MDAs in Ekiti State, Nigeria, and evaluated the influence of the government-integrated financial management information system (GIFMIS) on transparency in the same federal MDAs as the study pertains to the regulations of financial management and transparency. H₀: there is no significant relationship between financial administration regulations and transparency inside federal ministries, departments, and agencies in Nigeria. The study is domiciled to federal ministries, departments, and agencies in Ekiti State. The selection of the three variables and objectives was to assess the impact of TSA, IPPIS, and GIFMIS on transparency across federal ministries, departments, and agencies in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW**2.1 Conceptual Review****2.1.1 Transparency**

El Hamad et al. (2025) indicated that transparency is the act of accountability for one's actions, decisions, and behavior. It is taking the successes and failures and not blaming others for the wrong actions taken. It involves a duty to manage, monitor, and report financial resources. In a broad sense, it will cover everything that pertains to openness in terms of budgeting, spending, and financial decision-making by the public or not-for-profit sectors (Bello & Thomas, 2025). Transparency addresses accountability by an individual or team in terms of being responsible for one's role or work results; it also entails openness concerning progress responsibilities met and decisions to stakeholders or workmates (Okolie & Egbon, 2025). Transparency is a mechanism of check and balance to make sure that individuals, organizations, or agencies carry out their functions and duties that is, being accountable to norms and there exist mechanisms to oversee operations in place to try to ensure compliance and correct shortfalls or wrongdoing (Chizoba & Onuora, 2025). Transparency implies liability or transparency to answer before the law for all those actions, the commission of which may entail punishment for acts considered illegal or against the rule of law.

2.1.2 Financial Administration Rules

Principles of financial management address planning, organizing, procurement, and utilization of the government's money as well as policy formulation for the right things to achieve the aspirations of members of such a society, public financial management is the link between resources and aspirations of the community on one hand and the future and the present on the other hand (Akpanowo & Mbobo, 2025). Financial administration rules are at the very heart of the fiscal operation and policy of the government that handling money is costly and hazardous for all parties involved in the circulation chain with safer and less costly for a merchant to pay with a debit or credit card than to pay with money (Śwital & Kobylski, 2023). With the lowest possible idle funds invested in alternative financial instruments financial administration rules help the government to have enough liquidity for everyday expenses like paying suppliers, bills, and wages (Ezeagu et al., 2022). Investment plan choices for excess funds are likewise covered by the Financial administration policy, including the establishment of procedures to invest excess funds in low-risk, short-term investments that have returned for the business while remaining liquid. Adeniji et al. (2025) state that financial administration standards form the foundation of internal controls that avoid theft, fraud, and errors in handling cash through checks and balances like job segregation, prompt reconciliations, approval procedures, and ensuring that the money is accounted for and recorded properly are examples of controls.

2.1.2.1 Treasury Single Account (TSA)

The Treasury Single Account (TSA) is a unified system used by the governments whereby the entire revenue of the public will be paid into a single account a chain of interlinking accounts. It unifies the receptions, disbursements, and financial activity of the government towards better control of the government and public finance transparency (JP et al., 2022). The Financial administration system allows one account to keep all government funds to steer clear of having government bank accounts set up to raises liquidity management by the reduction of the cost of borrowing and allows efficient monitoring of cash flow (Amahalu et al., 2022). A Treasury Single Account is a fiscal arrangement in which all the financial resources of government ministries, departments, and agencies are consolidated in a single account to enhance transparency in public finance and allow correct reporting and monitoring in real time (Okolie & Egbon, 2025). The TSA is a consolidation approach adopted by the government where all the public money is kept in a single account or an interlinked chain of accounts to bring more government control and transparency in the public finances, it brings the government's revenue, expenditure, and financial transactions together at the center (Kure & Salisu, 2024). To avoid the accumulation of government accounts, the system of financial administration permits a unified account to maintain all the money of the government by lowering the costs of borrowing, the TSA also improves liquidity management and guarantees smooth management of cash (Akpanowo & Mbobo, 2025). One account accumulates all the government departments' agencies' and ministries' money under a financial system known as the Treasury Single Account.

2.1.2.2 Government Integrated Financial Information System (GIFMIS)

Olabode and Adetoro (2023) posit that government integrated financial information system (GIFMIS) is a unified software platform, GIFMIS, which was thus developed to enhance the effectiveness of government finance management processes that facilitates centralization and automation of public financial processes, such as accounting,

reporting, and budgeting, with accuracy, transparency, and efficiency in the administration of public funds. Every financial transaction is accounted for, reported, and tracked due to the Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS), which integrates government financial management and provides an integrated approach to managing the financial activities of the public sector very effectively, like monitoring expenses and making budgets (Iwedi, 2024). GIFMIS provides the most sophisticated integrated public financial management system, which consolidates various government financial systems into one platform to allow the easier management of public resources better and thus enhanced coordination and real-time monitoring to fight corruption by constantly monitoring collections of revenues, budget implementation, and expenditure estimation, and supports an open and transparent manner of managing public finances (Kadir et al. (2024; Chukwudum & Joshua, 2024),. By consolidating all government fiscal management functions into one entity, GIFMIS puts a stop to corruption by keeping a constant track of revenue collections, budget implementations, and expenditure estimations and further facilitates the management of public finances transparently and openly (Ogbonna & Ojeaburu, 2015).

2.1.2.4 Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System (IPPIS)

Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System (IPPIS) is an online platform seeking to streamline government agencies' personnel and payroll functions to ensure transparency, accountability, and clean payments in the public sector (Iwedi, 2024). The scheme captures essential details like information about employees, salaries, and other benefits to ensure compliance with governance (Ogbonna & Ojeaburu, 2015). Through the removal of manual intervention, IPPIS reduces discrepancies and forgery along with improving effectiveness in managing personnel to enhance budgeting and reporting through facilitating access to and examination of real-time information. IPPIS also supports effective financial management in the public sector (Adeniji, et al., 2025; Kadir et al., 2024; El-Yaqub, 2021).

2.2 Theoretical Review

The study depends mainly on the two theories mentioned below: Public Financial Management Theory (PFM) and Theory of Financial Regulation. Thus, the study depends on Public Financial Management Theory (PFM) since it involves proper allocation, utilization, and accountability of public funds. PFM theory provides a guide to studying systems and policies supporting transparency and effectiveness in government finance management.

2.2.1 Public Financial Management Theory (PFM)

Public Financial Management (PFM) Theory addresses the processes, system, and policy used by the government to effectively and transparently manage public finance. El-Yaqub (2021) developed the theory and highlights the necessity for budgeting, accounting, and auditing processes so that financial resources can be made effective in fulfilling public needs. PFM theory facilitates accountability in managing public funds to enhance the delivery of services as well as fostering economic stability (Adekoya, 2023). This theory underscores the position of governance institutions in supporting fiscal responsibility and the fight against corruption. By the inclusion of stakeholder engagement, PFM theory emphasizes the need for the trust of citizens in government financial activities to enhance public sector financial performance towards sustainable development by highlighting efficiency, accountability, and transparency in public spending and budgeting (Amah, & Okpala, 2021). PFM assumes that increased bureaucratic control will result in more effective financial management and better use of resources (Adekoya, 2023). One of the biggest weaknesses of PFM is that sometimes technical control and efficiency are valued at the cost of increased public participation and openness over democratic accountability (Tetteh et al., 2021).

2.2.2 Theory of Financial Regulation

The Financial Regulation Theory was developed in its entirety by academics such as George Stigler (1971) and later expanded by Lawrence Summers and others in the late 20th century. The theory supports the intervention of the government in financial markets to correct market failure, mitigate systemic risk, and enhance equity. The Financial Regulation Theory is concerned with the necessity to regulate financial markets for the sake of stability, protection of customers, and mitigating systemic risk. (Alley, 2022). The theory holds the view that free markets are prone to inefficiency, market failure, and crises, sometimes fueled by moral hazard and too much risk-taking. Good regulation is about balancing safety and innovation To get financial institutions to behave responsibly and openly encourage a system that balances individual incentives and the wider good (Ndigwe et al., 2020). Regulators must be sensitive, reacting to changing market forces without letting their grip loosen due to their regulatory frameworks necessary to guard consumers and advance the stability of the financial sector. However, a vital criticism is that regulation tends to

create regulatory capture, whereby financial firms exercise an influence over regulators who have authority over them, thus undermining the intent of the legislation (Iwedi, 2024; Zakariyau & Mustapha, 2021; Uddin et al., 2020).

2.3 Empirical Review

Akpanowo and Mbobo (2025) determine the impact of the Fiscal Responsibility Act on budgeting and fiscal discipline in the public sector of Nigeria. Their study employed survey research methods and primary data collected through the questionnaire was analyzed. The sample population for the study was the entire staff working in the Ministry of Finance, which is roughly 500, out of which a sample size of 55 was selected using purposive sampling. These 55 respondents were chosen as they possessed some knowledge of accounting and finance. The study's hypotheses were analyzed through OLS regression algorithm and the software used was SPSS version 21. The study concluded that the Fiscal Responsibility Act has some effect on its implementation in Nigeria; the Fiscal Responsibility Act has some effects on fiscal responsibility in Nigeria; the Fiscal Responsibility Act has some effects on corruption control in Nigeria. Ibitoye et al. (2025) studied the nexus between poverty reduction and financial inclusion in Nigeria from 2013 to 2023. Financial inclusion, which refers to the access of a large segment of the population to a variety of advanced financial services, is critical to the development of an economy and is a strategic weapon to combat poverty. The authors focused on primary data collection through a survey.

While evaluating the roles of public administration in Nigeria concerning the issues of anti-corruption measures, Okolie and Egbon (2025) brought out the work of anti-corruption bodies. They used a historical research approach to study the development and relevance of agencies such as the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC). The relationship between the administrative systems and anti-corruption policies was analyzed through the lens of Institutional Theory. Their study provides new insights into the effectiveness of these anti-corruption bodies on the so-called 'successes' and 'defeats' of such bodies, which stem from underfunding and political interference. According to their findings, although these agencies have performed exceedingly well, their success is still hampered by factors like political interference, weak institutional structure, and poor headquarters. Chizoba and Onuora (2025) studied how the digital transformation of public administration in Nigeria changed accountability and transparency in the sector. This research is very critical because it corroborates digital integration in the MDAs of Anambra State in as far as accountability and transparency are taken in public sector. The authors used a survey research design to collect data through a questionnaire survey to the subjects of the study. They established that, at a 5% level of significance, the adoption of IPPIS and TSA led to enhanced levels of accountability and transparency in the federal government MDAs in Nigeria.

Bello and Thomas (2025) focused on how these technologies can be utilized to offer privacy, security, and transparency while preventing ghost worker fraud. Auditable and transparent payroll systems that are properly designed can result in tremendous savings for the government that is otherwise wasted in fraudulent activities. The conclusion of the study was that ghost worker fraud is a highly prevalent issue in public sector employment practices resulting in a loss of revenues, productivity, and increasing corruption. Ghost worker fraud and hiring in the public sector may be alleviated using Blockchain technology in various innovative ways.

To enhance the performance of Abubakar et al (2025), trying to accomplish construction projects in time studied key success factors in the implementation of project management information systems by construction companies. Data on the use of PMIS was collected from Kano State construction companies through questionnaires filled by knowledgeable persons. Descriptive and inferential statistics were performed using SPSS 25.0 to a set of data that was extracted from the questionnaire survey. Some of the "Willing to recommend PMIS to others" and "Willing to donate for PMIS adoption" scored the highest mean within their research criteria. Titus et al. (2025) were interested in the reasons behind the overcost in governance and its impact on the socioeconomic development of Nigeria. There is a shift of focus in the study as high cost of governance in Nigeria is due to over bureaucracy together with poor resource management and high level of corrupt practices. Furthermore, their analysis revealed that the immense over expenditure in governance has caused a deep deficit within the nation's budget alongside a sizable degree of the debt burden. Lessons Learned and Best Practices on Nigeria's Anti-Corruption War: 2015-2023 was written by Ibekaku-Nwagwu (2025). The Compendium is a milestone in the documentation and distillation of lessons learnt and best practices in Nigeria's anti-corruption campaigns between 2015 and 2023. The Compendium unveils Nigeria's stellar battle against corruption over the last eight years when the country showcased resilience, tenacity, and unyielding commitment that is reflective of Nigeria's commitment to good governance, accountability, and transparency.

Okeke et al. (2023) considered the effect of TSA on the cost of governance in the public sector in Nigeria. Used a descriptive and survey research design. The study population were ten Federal Ministries, Departments & Agencies (MDAs) in Anambra State. From primary data collected from a standardized questionnaire and selective sampling, their study selected 10 respondents per MDA. Based on their data, TSA and e-accounting significantly reduce leaks, which increase national spending, but with no impact on money nationally generated. Consequently, TSA and e-accounting have significant impacts on the cost of governance. In 2024, Simon and colleagues analyzed how the Electronic Payment System (EPS) and the Treasury Single Account (TSA) changed the financial performance of Development Finance Institutions (DFIs) in Nigeria. From 2007 to 2022, data from six selected DFIs in Nigeria (Bank of Industry BOI, Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria FMBN, Bank of Agriculture BOA, Nigeria Export-Import Bank NEXIM, The Infrastructure Bank, Development Bank of Nigeria) were analyzed using panel regression by means of purposive sampling technique with E-Views 12 Software. Their findings suggest that the conventional methods of revenue collection and payment processing used in DFIs were found to have an insignificant effect on the financial performance of DFIs. The study also found that liquidity and operational efficiency together with financial performance and stability were greatly enhanced by the application of the EPS and TSA systems.

The TSA Policy and how it affects economic development are succinctly dealt with by JP et al. (2022), in addition to citing the ethical concerns and accounting complications that have developed as a result of TSA application. The method used in the research was meta-analysis. Analysis of trends of government revenues during 2010-2019 was carried out. Pre-TSA and post-TSA eras were under scrutiny. Relative to the pre-TSA period, their findings were that overall government revenue appears to have plateaued after TSA introduction, suggesting that even with TSA introduction, government revenue collection is still very low. In South-East and South-South Nigeria, Amahalu et al. (2022) investigated the nexus between the Treasury Single Account and accountability in the Nigerian public sector. The field survey was the research design employed in this study. Twelve hundred and fifty Account Department employees in five Federal Universities Teaching Hospitals and five Federal Medical Centres in South-East and South-South Nigeria made up the population. Three hundred and three was the sample size calculated by the application of the Taro Yamane formula. 218 of the 303 copies of the questionnaire sent out were returned. Validity and reliability of the tool were tested. Inferential statistics such as Spearman's Correlation, Paired T-assess, and Cronbach Alpha were utilized to test hypotheses on SPSS version 23. Their results specifically revealed that there is a very high positive correlation between accountability and transactions workflow management, a very high positive correlation between accountability and chart of accounts management, a very high positive correlation between accountability and treasury management, and a very high positive correlation between accountability and transactions monitoring. Literature on the specific challenges and success of financial management controls in Nigerian Federal Ministries, Departments, and Agencies, particularly at the state level, is scarce due to growing attention to financial openness and transparency in public administration across the globe. Despite the fact that research has examined Nigeria's wider fiscal management systems, research that has examined how financial administration rules are implemented and the effectiveness of transparency mechanisms within federal MDAs throughout the state levels- for example, in Ekiti State- remains scant.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The data for this study were collected through survey research. This was utilized because the research directly gathered the data from respondents. The major data were collected in this research by employing the use of a questionnaire. Data obtained in this study were subjected to descriptive and ordinary least square regression analysis. The population of the study consists of 253 Federal Ministries, Department and Agencies MDAs heads in Ekiti State (Source: meeting attendance registered, 2024). The sample size of 150 heads of federal MDAs in Ekiti State were selected using the Purposive Sampling Technique to select active service members of federal MDAs. The baseline model employed by the study of Effiong et al. (2017) that evaluated the effect of Treasury Single Account (TSA) and the adoption of the Integrated Financial Management Information System (FMIS) on fraud management in Nigeria's public sector is given below:

$$FMPS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PCTSA + \beta_2 IPPIS + \beta_3 IFMIS + e \quad (i)$$

Where FMPS represents Fraud Management in the Public Sector, TSA indicates Treasury Single Account (TSA), GIFMIS indicates Government Integrated Financial Management Information System, IPPIS represents Integrated

Personnel Payroll Information System and e is the error term. However, the above model was modified to capture transparency which the previous studies failed to capture as follows:

$$TRAS_t = f(GIFMIS) \quad (ii)$$

Where $TRAS$ represents the Transparency indicator variable, FAR represents Financial administration rules. For the study, the $TRAS$ represents Transparency while the financial administration rules (FAR) were proxies by the Treasury Single Account (TSA), Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS), and Integrated Personnel Payroll Information System (IPPIS).

$$TRAS_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TSA_t + \beta_2 GIFMIS_t + e_t \quad (iii)$$

Where A represents Transparency, TSA indicates Treasury Single Account (TSA), $GIFMIS$ indicates Government Integrated Financial Management Information System. In line with the previous studies reviewed, the expectation is that financial administration rules have a positive and significant effect on transparency in the public sector. The *a priori* expectation is stated thus, β_1, β_2 & $\beta_3 > 0$. The independent variable of this study was financial administration rules which were measures by the Treasury Single Account (TSA), and Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS). While the dependent variable is transparency measured by transparency. A designed and structured questionnaire was used for data collection using four scales of 4 to 1. Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1). A pilot survey research was conducted on a group of respondents to validate the questionnaire with a factor reliability test using validity test results to show that there is excellent reliability for all the variables, with Cronbach's Alpha from 0.677 to 0.813. Specifically, Transparency (0.713), Treasury Single Account (0.762), Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (0.677), and Integrated Personnel Payroll Information System (0.813) are all acceptable as regards the internal consistency of the variables. Therefore, the level of alpha was considered to be reliable enough to proceed with the data analysis.

Table 1: Result of Validity and Reliability Test

Variables	Cronbach Alpha	No of items
Transparency	0.713	9
Treasury single account	0.762	9
Government integrated financial management information system	0.677	9
Integrated Personnel Payroll Information System	0.813	9

Source: Author's Computation, (2025)

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT

4.1 Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics for the four variables $TRAS$, TSA , $IPPIS$, and $GIFMIS$ are presented in the table 2 below. The highest mean value is TSA (38.301), followed by $GIFMIS$ (25.230), $IPPIS$ (27.476), $TRAS$ (23.925), and C (1.000). The medians correlate closely with the means, which reflects comparatively symmetric distributions for most of the variables except C . The range of variation is best explained by maximum and minimum value and the greatest spread falling to $TRAS$ between 12.019 and 28.451. The standard deviations are all of similar magnitude save C , which did not vary. Negative skewness values for the majority of variables suggest left-tailed distributions with the most pronounced skew being for $TRAS$ and $GIFMIS$. High kurtosis values for $TRAS$, TSA , and $IPPIS$ suggest a leptokurtic distribution with sharper peaks than normal. The Jarque-Bera test shows large normality deviations for all variables, with p -values of below 0.000, non-normal distributions.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Sta.	TRAS	C	TSA	IPPIS	GIFMIS
Mean	23.925	1.000	38.301	27.476	25.230
Median	25.134	1.000	39.705	31.521	26.593
Maximum	28.451	1.000	45.362	44.318	30.988
Minimum	12.019	1.000	27.417	26.008	13.418
Std. Dev.	4.112	0.000	3.611	3.965	3.480

Skewness	-1.838	0.000	-1.475	-1.803	-1.839
Kurtosis	4.572	0.000	4.538	4.328	2.710
Jarque-Bera	29.882	0.000	46.446	46.335	63.931
Probability	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Sum	3271.321	136.000	4842.726	353.829	483.159
Sum Sq. Dev.	2570.552	0.000	2120.320	2811.351	2906.112
Observations	136	136	136	136	136

Source: Author's Computation, (2025)

4.2 Impact of Financial Administration Rules on Transparency

The regression model of the impact of financial administration rules on transparency indicates that there are several variables statistically connected with transparency. The value of the t-statistic for Financial Administration Rules (FAR) is 6.5312 and the FAR coefficient is 0.6942 (p-value = 0.0122), suggesting that FAR is positively connected with transparency. In addition, the Treasury Single Account (TSA) and the Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS) both have extremely high positive coefficients of 0.5972 and 0.7052, respectively, with p-values of 0.0500 and 0.0000, which indicates that they contribute to increasing transparency. Besides, the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) is also very relevant with a coefficient of 0.6409 and a t-statistic of 5.5204 (p-value = 0.0000), attesting to its contribution towards enhancing transparency. The R-squared of 0.7811 indicates that approximately 78% of the difference in transparency is explained by the independent variables of the model. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.6932 adjusts for the number of predictors and signifies a good model fit. The f-statistic of 57.949 (p-value = 0.0000) and the Durbin-Watson value of 1.936 imply the model is significant statistically with no significant autocorrelation. All in all, the results conclude that regulations to financial administration such as FAR, TSA, GIFMIS, and IPPIS significantly affect transparency, where the most effective GIFMIS and IPPIS are.

Table 3: Regression Analysis on the Impact of Financial Administration Rules on Transparency in the federal MDAs in Nigeria

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.5722	2.0320	1.2469	0.2092
FAR	0.6942	0.0643	6.5312	0.0122
TSA	0.5972	0.0466	5.1348	0.0500
GIFMIS	0.7052	0.1242	6.3409	0.0000
IPPIS	0.6409	0.1026	5.5204	0.0000
R-squared	0.7811	Mean dependent var		25.064
Adjusted R-squared	0.6932	S.D. dependent var		4.326
S.E. of regression	3.4401	Akaike info criterion		5.869
Sum squared resid	1536.162	Schwarz criterion		5.062
Log likelihood	-335.023	Hannan-Quinn criter.		5.484
F-statistic	57.949	Durbin-Watson stat		1.936
Prob (F-statistic)	0.0000			

Source: Author's Computation, (2025)

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The regression model explaining the impact of financial administration regulations (FAR) on transparency illustrates a statistically significant and positive relationship between government financial management transparency and financial administration practices. The primary findings, while maintaining robust statistical relationships, and by previous studies and frameworks in the public financial management (PFM) field. The value of the t-statistic 6.5312

(p-value = 0.0122), for FAR with a coefficient of 0.6942 indicates a high positive correlation with transparency. The study suggests that good financial administration rules have a direct relationship with more transparency in the management of public funds. The study supports the findings of Okeke et al. (2023) which considered the effect of TSA on the cost of governance in the public sector in Nigeria. Their findings revealed that TSA and e-accounting significantly reduce leaks, which increase national spending, but with no impact on money nationally generated. Consequently, TSA and e-accounting have significant impacts on the cost of governance.

The findings of this study negated the findings in the study of Simon (2024) their findings revealed that the conventional methods of revenue collection and payment processing used in DFIs were found to have an insignificant effect on the financial performance of DFIs. Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) with a coefficient of 0.6409 and t-statistic of 5.5204 (p-value = 0.0000), the IPPIS also positively contributes to transparency has the scheme avoids payroll fraud and only genuine employees are paid, and controls personnel expenditures appropriately. This is consistent with the study done by Chizoba and Onuora (2025) studied how the digital transformation of public administration in Nigeria changed accountability and transparency in the sector. This research is very critical because it corroborates digital integration in the MDAs of Anambra State as far as accountability and transparency are taken in public sector organisations of Nigeria. The authors used a survey research design to collect data through a questionnaire survey to the subjects of the study. They established that, at a 5% level of significance, the adoption of IPPIS and TSA led to enhanced levels of accountability and transparency in the federal government MDAs in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the regression model gave very strong support to the hypothesis that some of the financial administration instruments and practices specifically FAR, TSA, GIFMIS, and IPPIS all play a significant role in improving transparency in public financial management. Findings are in line with earlier studies, which have consistently established that good, integrated systems and effective regulatory regimes are prerequisites for guaranteeing transparency, accountability, and preventing corruption in the public sector. The findings provide conclusive evidence that the improvement of these fiscal management tools needs to remain a priority with governments aiming at making their fiscal activities more transparent and accountable. Financial administration regulations, such as the Financial Administration Rules (FAR), Treasury Single Account (TSA), Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS), and Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS), should still be reinforced and enforced to enhance transparency. GIFMIS and IPPIS must be prioritized further to optimize and enhance their usage in relevant industries in a manner that will have a greater impact. The study also proposed that there be frequent reviews for considering the continuous effectiveness of such systems and if they are incorporating adjustments based on emerging financial concerns. Additionally, it should also consider whether the depth and breadth of such systems can be expanded to bring greater accountability and transparency to general government activity.

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